

**METHOD AND COMBINED MACHINE FOR TURNING SOIL PLATES
TO FORM AN IRRIGATION DRILL IN POLICE**

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Annotation. The article is based on the method of overturning soil clods to form an irrigation ditch and the combined machine that implements it.

Keywords: Field crops, combined machine, body, guide plate, soil, quality of work, fertilizer, irrigation canal, unevenness of the field, planting area.

Introduction.

The problems of high-quality tillage of the soil with minimum energy costs for planting polys crops have been considered in many scientific works [1-12]. Researches were conducted by V.I.Malyukov [1], D.Sh.Chuyanov [3-6] and others on the creation of machines for police, justification of their construction and justification of the parameters of their working bodies. The construction and parameters of the machines that till the soil before planting and planting in the cultivation of polys crops are based on V.G. Abezin, N.V. Aldoshin and V.I. Malyukov. Ya.P.Lobachesky, F.M.Mamatov and I.T.Ergashev studied the processes of turning the blade by 180 degrees at the limit of its edge [4-6]. These studies did not consider the issues of preparing the soil for planting poly crops in one pass with minimal tillage.

The purpose of the study is to justify the method and combined machine for turning the soil flats to form an irrigation ditch for planting rice crops.

Materials and methods. Scientists of the Scientific Research Institute of Vegetables, Poly crops and Potatoes of Uzbekistan recommended planting poly

crops in $\{(290+70)/2\} \cdot 70$ or $\{(270+90)/2\} \cdot 70$ schemes, and on this basis planting in most land areas of our republic work is being carried out[1]. In this case, deep tillage (20-30 cm) with the formation of an irrigation ditch between the main row of planting (70 or 90 cm), it is advisable to treat the surface (15-20 cm) and give ribbon fertilizer to the bush (270 or 290 cm).

The method of overturning the soil slabs to form an irrigation ditch for planting rice crops is carried out with a screw casing and a guide plate in the following sequence (Fig. 1).

Each plot of the planting area with a width of $b=Bc/2$ is cut from the soil mass in a vertical plane using disk-shaped knives (case I). Then, under the influence of the plow, each blade is separated from the bottom of the egg. The subsequent overturning of the blades to a certain position relative to each other occurs under the mutual influence of the right and left overturning bodies and guide plates. First, each body 1 affects the lower edge of the blade and raises it, and the guiding plate 2 affects the side edge of the blade and pushes it towards the body (case II). In the initial phase, when the blades are overturned under the influence of the body and the guide plate, their centers of gravity should not move to the side in the transverse plane.

As the blade is turned, the guide plate gradually shifts its effect from the bottom to the top.

When the bottom edge of each blade is at a distance of $(b/2) < e > 0$ from the initial position, the guide plate ends its action, and further overturning of the blade is done only by the action of the tipper (case IV). As a result, the upper side of the palaxa rests on the untreated soil (case V). Overturning of the blade is carried out at a length L (Fig. 1), which is called the length of twisting of the blade.

Performance indicators of the combined machine Tst 63.04:2001 "Ispytaniya selskohozyaystvennoy tekhniki. Machines and tools poverkhnostnoy obrabotki pochvy. Program and methods of testing" and Tst 63.02:2001 "Testing

of agricultural technology. Machines and tools for deep machining. It was determined according to "Programa i metody ispytaniy".

1 – the main rotating body; 2 – guide plate

Figure 1. Create a ditch for irrigation of soil plots method of conversion

The object of the study is the guiding plate housings, which work on the planting area of polys crops. The study of the technological work processes of the plate casings of the combined machine was carried out according to the literature sources and the results of testing in field conditions [11,12].

Taking into account the results of theoretical studies, an experimental device equipped with plate casings, which are directed to the planting area for plowing, was made for conducting laboratory-field experiments.

Researches were conducted in the fields of Sertepa farm of Kashkadarya region. In the tests, the machine was assembled with the Arion-630C tractor. In the experimental studies, the issues of the influence of the length of the guide plate and the depth of processing on the performance of the bodies were studied.

Completeness of burial of plant residues in the planting area was determined by the mass of plant residues and weeds remaining unburied on the soil surface. Counting of unburied plant debris and weeds was carried out in plots 5 m long and the width equal to the coverage width of the hulls. Unburied plant remains were collected and weighed on the scale with an error of ± 10 g.

The depth of burial of plant residues was determined by measuring the distance from the surface of the plow to the upper limits of the placement of plant residues. Two vertical cuts were made in each pass. Measurements were made with an accuracy of ± 0.5 cm and in quadruplicate.

Results and discussion. In the implementation of the proposed technology, i.e., the formation of the primary irrigation ditch with high-quality overturning of the blades is influenced by the coverage width of the casings, the length of the guide plate, and the depth of processing.

When determining the effect of the length of the guide plate on the energy and quality indicators of the casings, the depth of processing was $a=25$ cm, the speed of the device was 1.72 m/s, the coverage width of each casing was 52.5 cm, and the coverage width of the device was 105 cm.

According to the results of experimental studies (Table 1), it was found that the length of the guide plate has a significant effect on the overturning of the blades and the profile of the plow.

When the casings are operated without a guide plate, the blades are mainly

laid on the untreated field surface to the right and left, respectively. In this case, the width of the treated area in the middle is 103.2 cm and the depth is 31.8 cm. an open egat is formed. When the length of the guide plate is $l_z=40$ cm, cases of incomplete overturning of the blade were observed, and an open egate with a width of 91.6 cm and a depth of 29.8 cm was formed. When the length of the guide plate was further increased, the technological process went reliably.

Table 1

Effect of guide plate length on device performance

The name and dimensions of indicators	The length of the guide plate, m					
	0	0,20	0,40	0,60	0,80	0,93
Aggregate speed, m/c	1,72	1,72	1,72	1,72	1,72	1,72
Processing depth, cm: M_{cp} $\pm\sigma$, cm	24,9 1,8	24,7 1,7	24,6 1,5	24,3 1,4	24,2 1,4	24,2 1,3
Width of coverage; M_{cp} $\pm\sigma$, cm	101,5 4,8	104,5 4,4	104,3 3,8	105,4 3,5	105,7 3,3	105,9 3,3
The width of the ditch, cm	103,2	96,2	91,6	78,2	60,2	21,6
Ditch depth, cm	31,8	30,3	29,8	29,1	28,8	9,8
Burial completeness of plant remains, %	49,8	59,3	66,0	79,5	90,3	92,3
Average burial depth of plant remains, cm	3,3	3,9	7,2	10,4	11,3	13,2
Soil fertility, %	37,1	48,6	64,8	71,5	73,2	77,9
Tensile strength, kN	9,6	9,9	10,6	10,8	11,1	11,6

When the length of the guide plate was 93 cm, each blade was turned over

on its edge, and the depth of the trench formed in the middle of the processing area was 9.8 cm. In this case, the guide plate affects the blade from the beginning of its rise to its full rollover, i.e. 160-1700 turns.

When the length of the guide plate is $l_z=80$ cm, a groove with a width of 60.2 cm and a depth of 28.8 cm is formed, which meets the requirements of the proposed technology.

Weed burial follows a convex curve when the coverage width of the device is 105 cm, the coverage width of the housings is 52.5 cm, and the length of the guide plate is 80 cm (Figure 2). In the range of 22-26 cm of processing depth, the burial completeness of the mass of plant residues was up to 91-93%, that is, at the level of requirements. It can be seen from the graph (Fig. 2) that with the increase of processing depth α , the tensile strength of casings R increases. With the increase of processing depth a from 22 to 30 cm, the tensile strength increases by 15.3%. Thus, it was determined that the completeness of burial of the mass of plant residues in the range of 22-26 cm of the rational processing depth of the casings is within the agrotechnical requirements.

Figure 2. Variation of the tensile strength of the casings R and the completeness of

burial D of the mass of plant residues depending on the depth of their processing

The proposed new method of preparing the land for planting in policing (Fig. 3) is carried out with the help of a combined machine [2] developed at the Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics [5]. Combined machine (Fig. 4) frame 1 and suspension device 2 installed on it, disk blade 3, screw housings 4 and 5 turning right and left, guide plate 6, flat cutters 7, support wheels 8, roller 9, deep softener consists of softener 10 and fertilizer application device 11.

Figure 3. Construction scheme of the combined machine frame; 2- suspension device; 3-disk blade; 4 th and 5-th left and right tilting bodies; 6-guide plate; 7-flats; 8-th base wheel; 9-th reel.

Figure 3 shows the overview of the combination machine.

Figure 4. General (side) view of the combined unit with the Arion-630C tractor

In the tests, the tillage depth of the area where the seeds are planted was determined as 24 cm, and in practice, its average value was 24.9 cm. The amount of fractions smaller than 50 mm was on average 79.1 percent, and the unevenness of the treated field surface was 4.4 cm.

The width of the upper part of the irrigation ditch was 60.4 cm, and the depth of the irrigation ditch was 23.4 cm. This makes it possible to sow the seeds of rice crops in the upper part of the ditch in two rows, with a distance of 60, 70 or 90 cm between the main rows.

Conclusion. The laws of change of the resistance of the guide plate body depending on its structural parameters, the working procedure and the properties of the soil were determined. With low energy consumption, tilting of the blades relative to each other and formation of the initial irrigation ditch is ensured when the covering width of the casings is 52.5 cm and the length of the guide plate is 80 cm.

Reference

1. Malyukov V.I. Mechanization of horticulture. - Volgograd, Nij.-Volzh. Kn. izd-vo, 1982. - S. 6-14.
2. [Chuyanov, D.Sh.](#), [Mamatov, F.M.](#), [Shodmonov, G.D.](#) Main parameters of manure sealer, E3S Web of Conferences, 2023, 401, 04031
3. Patent RUz No. IAR 04004. Sposob obrabotki pochvy i poseva / Mamatov F.M., Chuyanov D.Sh., Khudoyarov B.M., Ergashev G.Kh., Gulboev S.I. // Official newsletter. – 2009. – No. 9.
4. Patent RUz No. FAP 00657. Combinirovannoe orudie dlya obrabotki pochvy i poseva / Mamatov F.M., Mirzaev B.S., Chuyanov D.Sh., Ergashev G.Kh., Quziev N.M., Shodmonov G.D. ., Temirova D.I., Ismailov I.I. // Official newsletter. – 2011. – No. 11.
5. Mamatov F.M., Chuyanov D.Sh., Mirzaev M.S., Ergashev G'.Kh. Pochvozashchitnaya technology podgotovki pochvy dlya poseva bakchevyx kultur. Materialy mejdunarodnoy conference "Scientific potential mira" - Warsaw, 2013. - P.57-59.
6. Mamatov F.M., Chuyanov D.Sh., Shodmonov G'.D. The combined unit that prepares the soil for planting rice crops // Agriculture of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2016. - No. 12. - B. 42.
7. Chuyanov, D., Shodmonov, G., Ergashov, G., Choriyev, I. Combination machine for soil preparation and sowing of gourds, E3S Web of Conferences, 2021, 264, 04035
8. Chuyanov, D., Shodmonov, G., Ismailov, I., Ergashov, G., Sadikov, A. Traction resistance of the combined machine plow, E3S Web of Conferences, 2021, 264, 04036
9. Chuyanov, D., Shodmonov, G., Avazov, I., Rashidov, N, Ochilov, S. Soil preparation machine parameters for the cultivation of cucurbitaceous crops //

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10. D. Chuyanov, U. Abdurakhmanov, G. Shodmonov, Energy-saving technology and machinery for growing melons // Novateur Publication India's International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology (IJIERT, India, 2020)

11. Dospekhov B.A. Methodology polevogo opyta. - Moscow: Kolos, 1979. - 416 p.

12. Vedenyapin V.V. Obshchaya metodika eksperimentalnogo issledovaniya i obrabotki opytnykh dannyx. - Moscow: Kolos, 1973. - 184 p.